

Comparing motivation and reflection in project-work between TBL and PBL

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Abstract

Project work in engineering courses prepares students with essential professional competencies, enables them to solve real problems, and develops critical skills for their future jobs. Given the challenges of executing projects with material products within tight deadlines, adopting suitable pedagogical approaches is crucial to the success of these projects. In this context, this study compares two pedagogical approaches in two courses with the same teacher in 2022 and 2023: Team-Based Learning (TBL) and Project-Based Learning (PBL), focusing on motivation, reflection, and learning. The students' perceptions were collected through an online survey. Responses came from 58/77 students for TBL and 56/78 for PBL, asking about their project-work experiences. The results demonstrate that both methodologies significantly enhance motivation and learning compared with traditional approaches. However, PBL uniquely encouraged more reflection and the practical application of theoretical knowledge. This analysis underscores the significance of tackling real problems and contexts, revealing that PBL provides a direct practical experience in engineering education. These insights are invaluable for educators and institutions aiming to refine their teaching methodologies, advocating for more integration of practical projects, and collaborative efforts into the engineering curriculum.

Keywords: Project-based learning; Engineering Education; Project Approaches; Motivation; Reflection.

1 Introduction

Education in the 21st century is experiencing significant cultural changes that imply an amotivation to study. For example, in Europe, it is approximately 11.7%, whereas in Colombia, 24.2% of young people aged 15–28 years are in tertiary education (DANE, 2023; Eurostat, 2023). This new culture requires the exploration of teaching methodologies that foster autonomy and personal development, resulting in high levels of motivation, and allowing students to acquire professional skills while remaining committed to the educational system. One methodology used to promote deep learning is Team-Based Learning (TBL), which follows a scheme similar to an inverted class and does not differ significantly from the structure of a traditional course. By contrast, problem-based learning (PBL) represents a more disruptive methodology regarding usual practices and promises to increase the learning of transverse skills. However, both methodologies must keep students motivated. In this article, we explore these two methodologies from the perspectives of motivation and reflection for learning. Initially, we reviewed the two methods. Subsequently, we explain the perspective used to interpret motivation and reflection based on the results of students' perceptions. Finally, we present the findings of this study.

2 Background

TBL is a pedagogical practice implemented in courses where students work as a team during sessions to reflect on a specific topic or the content of the subject. According to Michaelsen and Sweet (2008), TBL uses a scheme similar to that of the inverted class, in which students first prepare the subject assigned before addressing it in class. This method is divided into three stages: first, students study a particular topic; second, they participate in an individual reflection guided by the teacher; and third, they socialise reflection with their group, which remains constant throughout the course.

TBL is also a structured method for problem solving that is not limited to simple reflection. Sibley and Ostafichuk (2014) pointed out that TBL is designed to enable students to make group decisions about problems

by applying concepts learned in class. Its structure is based on four principles: a) group training is organised and planned; b) students are responsible for their work; c) tasks are oriented towards learning and teamwork development; and d) members must actively participate and be prepared for group discussions. These principles, which are based on constructivist learning theories, are carefully considered during course design to achieve expected learning results.

TBL encourages motivation by allowing students to make their own decisions during discussions while the group is progressively structured. According to Haidet et al. (2008), although the evidence is limited, some studies show little effect or the need to integrate other practices, such as active learning and teacher accompaniment. However, the systematic work of the groups helps mature the group and refine their goals and collective commitments, which encourages the motivation to work as a team.

Project-based learning (PBL) is a pedagogical practice in which students solve a problem within the framework of a planned and structured project. De Graaff and Kolmos (2003), as well as Rodríguez-Mesa (2018) on groups in Colombia, identified six essential principles of PBL: a) The problem is the central axis and comes from real situations, b) is interdisciplinary, c) the student, who formulates and directs learning, d) is done in a group, e) is applied in a sociocultural context, and f) promotes exemplary learning. According to Kolmos et al. (2009), PBL adapts its models to the specific learning needs and institutional conditions of each course, varying the duration of time dedicated to solving problems according to their complexity, which may require from one day to several weeks.

Learning theories that underlie both methodologies, TBL and PBL, share the ideas of theorists such as Vygotsky and Bruner, but differ in how they address cognitive development. TBL considers that learning goes through stages from dualism to commitment, including multiplicity and relativism, in which individual opinions are discussed in a group, promoting the development of neural networks through emotional involvement (Sibley & Ostafichuk, 2014). In contrast, PBL sees learning as three-dimensional, covering cognitive, motivational, and social aspects, with a strong base in sociocultural theories, where students are actively involved in the resolution of real problems, interacting, and acting together (Illeris, 2018).

In the context of these two educational practices, we present a qualitative case study to understand the differences in motivation and reflection between them. We used two groups of students from different semesters who applied the same methodology to solve a problem and obtain a designed product. Using an online survey with an open-ended question, we examined the following research questions: What effect does the implementation of TBL and PBL have on students' motivation and reflection about the content of their projects? Consequently, how do TBL and PBL compare their effects on students' critical reflection and motivation?

3 Methodology

Two editions of the same course aimed at mechanical and mechatronics engineering students were implemented, in which they had to demonstrate the skills acquired throughout their career in the design of a mechanical product. These courses were developed during the second semesters of 2022 and 2023.

We employ an online questionnaire comprising an open-ended query to gather students' perceptions of their learning experience: "Please describe your experience in this course." This approach was selected to obtain unbiased information that could be thoroughly analysed. The anticipated responses were expected to provide pertinent data on the aforementioned questions.

The analysis of the responses was conducted from the perspective of Ryan and Deci's (2017) self-determination theory and Donald Schön's (1983) theory of reflection. We used Braun and Clarke's (2006) thematic analysis of students' responses to search for patterns related to motivation, autonomy, connection, competence, and reflection, typical of SDT for both PBL and TBL. We then examined how these patterns influence different types of student motivation, such as intrinsic and extrinsic motivation based on autonomy, competence, and connection. Likewise, the relationship between reflection and motivation was included in each model.

3.1 Self-determination theory

Self-determination theory (SDT) is a model of human behaviour that describes motivation as a continuum from controlled to autonomous (Ryan & Deci, 2017). This theory maintains that motivation is not a unitary phenomenon but a set of influences that psychologically impact the will of the individual. Motivation may reflect intrinsic interests, which arise from an individual's desires, or may be extrinsic, induced by external pressures that force activities that are not valued personally.

According to Deci and Ryan, autonomy is crucial in determining how these influences affect will; therefore, motivation, whether internally perceived through personal beliefs and experiences or externally perceived through the actions of a pedagogical process, plays a fundamental role in this aspect.

Beyond autonomy, this theory also identifies competition and relationships as the basic needs that complement an individual's motivation. Competition refers to the need to feel effective and capable, manifested through curiosity, manipulation, and various epistemic motifs. Conversely, a relationship implies feeling socially connected. This is related to the feeling that others care about one another, generating a sense of belonging and social importance.

3.2 Reflection as an indicator of learning

A central aspect that demonstrates that educational processes generate learning is reflection. According to Donald Schön, reflection can occur in two ways: "in action" and "on action." The reflection "*in action*" occurs when participants respond to unexpected situations, which implies a constant evaluation of the ongoing events. On the other hand, the reflection "*on action*" takes place when students review and analyse their past performances after an event has occurred, with the aim of improving future actions.

3.3 Applied Engineering Project (AEP)

The Applied Engineering Project is a crucial subject in the curriculum of mechanical and mechanical engineering. The course, which extends for 16 weeks, with a total of 192 school hours, is at the end of each program. Its objective is for students to apply their knowledge in solving a specific engineering design problem using methodologies backed by academic literature and appropriate for the type of problem to be solved.

The course generally hosts between 60 and 70 students, and is divided into three groups. The weekly structure of the course includes combined sessions: a two-hour general session for all groups, where common design-related issues are discussed, and separate sessions of tutoring, where each group works independently with a dedicated teacher, for monitoring and advice in the design process as necessary.

The AEP originally combined direct teaching with the realisation of projects during the first ten years. However, in 2020, a significant change was implemented in the PBL model during the pandemic. This new approach gave students the total responsibility to define and document an adequate mechanical design methodology. Using the principles of PBL, the model emphasised the declaration of the problem, selection of the methodology, and its development under the complete autonomy of students.

The students, grouped into teams of five members, selected a project in the first week of working with a real client. This allowed them to understand the problem deeply and address the solution in a group and autonomous manner. This model was implemented in direct education, as described below.

3.3.1 Team-Based Learning Model for AEP

The framework used in the creation of class activities is shown on the right side of Figure 1. Students must review the assigned documents for each class session, which are carefully chosen by the AEP teachers. To guarantee that students finish the assigned reading, a session guide containing activities will be planned and supplied to them during the session using various discretionary methods depending on the activity. Students will have a total of 10–12 minutes to complete the activity.

The guide is then delivered to the teacher or auxiliary student. Students will meet in group work and solve the same guide or questions as in the group's consensus. In no case did the group respond to the same or paraphrase of one of the group's deliveries. Then, clarification was made regarding the non-consensus of the group and a complementary presentation of 30 minutes. If there are more doubts or clarity, the complementary presentation is trimmed proportionally.

TBL approach

PBL approach

Figure 1. Scheme of a 2 -hour for TBL (left) and PBL (right) sessions

General sessions:

(Theory)

- Activity 0: 5 min - Presentation of the teacher's guide

- Activity 1: 15 min + 2 min Collection
- Activity 2: 40 min + 3 min Collection
- Activity 3: Peer assessment (5 min)
- Rest: 10 min
- Activity 3: Non -consensus clarification (15 min)
- Activity 4: Complementary presentation of 20-25 min

Tutoring sessions (Application for the project work)

- Activity 0: 5 min - Presentation of the teacher's guide
- Activity 1: Individual project activity 20-22 min
- Activity 2: Activity Project in Group 70-73 min
- Activity 3: Peer assessment (5 min)
- Activity 4: Clarification of non-consensus (15-20 min)

We designed 12 TBL activities that covered most of the system-design methodology. The reading materials required by the students were distributed at the beginning of the course and organised into a schedule of detailed reading activities. In addition, in each session, reflection questions were asked to encourage analysis and discussion among the participants.

3.3.2 Project-based Learning Model for AEP

The PBL model focuses on students' project-work. Two weekly group sessions of two hours each were included. In the first session, all students met in a room to discuss a topic that was aligned with the general design methodology schedule. By 2022, it will work with 78 students.

In this model, students are responsible for selecting the subject, formulating the design problem, and applying the design methodology to find a solution. As in the TBL version, students were expected to present the design product after 14 weeks of work on the project. Class sessions focused on general explanations and were dedicated most of the time to the autonomous development of the project by students. The teacher played the role of supervisor. The second column of Figure illustrates this general procedure, which is less structured than the TBL model.

To avoid including dramatic changes in the processes that could influence the result, for both tests, the design methodology for the solution of the problem should be the design of the systems presented by NASA. (NASA SP-2016-6105 Rev 2, 2020).

4 Results

We collected 58 of the 76 possible responses for the TBL format and 56 of the 78 responses for PBL. In the TBL format of the course, a real problem was integrated. Specifically, during a session, the process described in the TBL methodology was followed, and in the following, it applied directly to the work of the project. This structure resulted in explicit comments from the students regarding their motivation. Some of the students' responses did not refer to the TBL or PBL models because they focused on difficulties with the group, especially in cases where they were excluded from the project work by the team members.

In the TBL model, a student commented on how working with a real project motivated the group to collaborate despite the challenges: "The development of the project was very enriching and the work with external parts was motivating; the work with the members of the group was productive and pleasant, and the final product had clear flaws, but an approach aimed at the target product. " Another student highlighted how the structure and process of course feedback favour the development of the project: "Being able to achieve the main objective was something very motivating for what I have left, the development of the course and

accompaniment, [...] because few teachers take the time to guide one and give feedback, in terms of group work made me grow academically and personally because I shared with very good classmates and personalities other than mine was interesting in addition to motivator. "

On the other hand, in the PBL model, students advance in each class session on the project, with only a few additional explanations. Motivation was influenced by the approach to a real project and freedom of thematic choice. A student said, 'I liked Pai a lot because I could realise the lines that most attracted my attention from the career seen holistically, it helped me to discover my preferences, and I liked the project a lot because it motivated me a lot to follow working with it once the subject of AEP ended. " Another added: "I honestly liked the project because I could implement many of the knowledge of the career and also the engineering skills, there were many things that did not remember how they were done, and only by reviewing a few notes, I managed to understand and remember."

In TBL, autonomy is remarkable, but seems to be more structured within the team's activities. A student mentioned: "The topics presented in class contributed great methodological aspects to the management of our project and the specific research for the project has generated new interests in technologies and tools." This observation suggests that although autonomy exists, it is guided by the structure of the course and the activities of the team.

Autonomy and personal exploration are fundamental in PBL. A student stressed: "He was also very challenging personally because I had to look 'real' project and play a role within him that I feel he had a lot of involvement in the final result. " This demonstrates that PBL allows students to make independent decisions and apply their knowledge in a practical and significant manner.

In summary, while TBL provides a structure that guides student participation, PBL offers more space for autonomy and personalisation of learning, which is crucial for student motivation and commitment.

In TBL, the connections between team members are strongly emphasised through collaboration. One student stressed, 'There was very good communication between all members, and although there were differences in ideas, everything was decided diplomatically and objectively'. Effective communication and collective decision making strengthen the link between team members, highlighting the importance of cooperation and understanding.

In PBL, although the connection is equally important, it seems more oriented towards interaction with the external context of the project. The relationship between professionals and the application of their work in real situations plays a crucial role. As a student said: "Work with external parts was motivating, the work with the group members was productive and pleasant." This indicates that in PBL, in addition to internal collaboration, connection with the external environment and practical relevance are essential components that motivate and enrich educational experience.

Regarding *reflection in the action*, on TBL, students experience continuous adaptation to solve problems. A student commented: "The project flowed very well, there were problems that were solved throughout the semester." Another added: "During the sessions, we frequently adjust our strategies based on how the project evolved."

In PBL, about the *reflection in the action*, a student stressed: "He was also very challenged personally because I had to look for ways to reach several results in the best way." Another said: "I was constantly evaluating and reassessing my methods as new challenges arose."

In TBL, *reflection on action* is a crucial part of learning, as a student's comment shows: "Seeing the evolution of the project from its conceptualization was incredibly satisfactory and rooted in the love of the career and the potential of it for me for my profession".

In PBL, students *reflect on* their experiences and results after their occurrence. An example is the comment: "Work with external parts was motivating, the work with the group members was productive and pleasant." Another student reflected: "At the end of the project, I evaluated how my contributions could have been more effective", indicating a detailed consideration of their actions and results.

5 Discussion

The main difference between TBL and PBL lies in how each approach motivates the students. In TBL, motivation arises when working with real problems within a team structure where the challenges are approached collectively. However, in PBL, motivation is influenced by individual autonomy and the challenges of the real project, with students motivated by the opportunity to directly apply their skills to complex and real problems, implying more personal and self-directed learning.

Regarding autonomy, students' responses suggest that PBL tends to foster more autonomous motivations because of its structure which allows greater autonomy and opportunities for students to pursue their interests and significantly apply their knowledge. In contrast, TBL, although effective, offers fewer opportunities for personalisation and application of learning in real contexts.

The PBL link extends to the relationship with the external context of the project, whereas the TBL link focuses more on the internal collaboration of the team. In terms of competition, TBL focuses on the understanding and application of the thematic structure of the designed exercises, whereas PBL develops around the application of previous knowledge and the solution of practical problems.

Both methods incorporate elements of reflection; however, there are notable differences in how and when this reflection occurs. In TBL, reflection is more structured and oriented towards group problem-solving. In PBL, reflection is more autonomous and integrated with the individual application of theory to practice, promoting individual *reflections on actions*. This could indicate that PBL offers more opportunities for personal development through reflection, while TBL promotes reflection, which strengthens collaboration and interpersonal skills.

Finally, PBL can be more effective in developing reflective professionals who can evaluate and adapt their behaviour autonomously. Meanwhile, TBL could be more appropriate for those who benefit from structured reflection in a collaborative environment, promoting the improvement of teamwork and collaborative strategies. Ultimately, PBL facilitates an environment in which students can act as reflexive professionals, continuously evaluating and adjusting their approaches, while TBL promotes reflection as a means of improving the collaboration and effectiveness of the team in problem-solving.

6 Conclusion and Future Perspectives

The two pedagogical practices have different effects on student motivation. On one hand, TBL has a structure that favours motivation when the group's composition is recurring and the activities carried out are around the same project during the semester. According to this case study of TBL, the integration of real problems during the sessions motivated students to collaborate and overcome challenges. Students' comments highlighted that the experience was useful for their personal and motivational development, driven by the structure of the

course and continuous feedback. This same structure favoured the reflection process, but limited it to the improvement of teamwork to enhance the assigned activities.

On the other hand, with less structured activities in curricular design, the PBL approach stood out for promoting greater autonomy, confirming students' learning principles, allowing students to make critical decisions, and applying their knowledge to complex problems. Thematic freedom and connections to real problems intensify motivation and commitment. However, these two approaches require an increase in the number of feedback cycles.

Based on these results, it is recommended to adopt TBL and PBL approaches to incorporate more TBL flexibility and a more collaborative structure in PBL, looking for a balance that maximises the strengths of both methods. The implementation of a real project on TBL that accompanied all activities could have a strong impact by increasing the motivation of the group.

A combination of TBL and PBL can have beneficial effects on online education. When there are real work limitations or difficulties in face-to-face meetings with students, as happened in the pandemic, the combination of these two methods, which highlights the approach of PBL autonomy and the challenge of the project, with online activities of TBL that allow structuring and favouring the remote participation of the students, could have an impact on new educational models.

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